

CATHOLIC UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF BUEA
(CUIB)

The Growth Mindset Entrepreneurial University

**DESIGN A MULTI-VENDOR E-COMMERCE APPLICATION USING
A PRODUCT RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM
A SENIOR YEAR PROJECT REPORT**

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SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN PARTIAL
FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF BACHELOR OF
SCIENCE (B.Sc.) DEGREE IN SOFTWARE ENGINEERING

SUPERVISOR

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May,2020

DECLARATION

I declare that this Project on “**DESIGN A MULTI-VENDOR E-COMMERCE APPLICATION USING A PRODUCT RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM**” is an original work done by me under the supervision of **Mme Tiako Fani Michele** of the school of Information Technology at the Catholic University Institute of Buea

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project titled “**DESIGN A MULTI-VENDOR E-COMMERCE APPLICATION USING A PRODUCT RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM**” was carried out by EYOMBO BASIL ADO registration number 18SI-004128, an undergraduate senior year student in the school of Information Technology of the Department of Software Engineering, Catholic University Institute of Buea.....

Date..... (student)

This Certification is Confirmed by:

Date.....

Supervisor Name (Supervisor / Supervisor Position)

Chapter 1

1. Introduction

This project is aimed on building an application that can interconnect different or multiple sellers together in one market place to sell their goods and services and create a large market with a variety of available goods for customers. It came to me when I had a video game I wanted to sell but for over a month I could not sell the game even after posting on some media platforms such as Whatsapp and Facebook groups. As a result, I developed the idea of creating a multivendor ecommerce platform where by different sellers can sign up to sell their goods and buyers can sign up to have access to a wide range of available goods and services. In addition, there is a recommendation system them will create a network amongst seller products such that at any point of search of a product, the recommender will recommend similar like products with other products that might be useful as you continue the buying process.

1.1 Background of the study

A multivendor e-commerce application is a platform that empowers multiple vendors to sell their products from one storefront. Multivendor store gives shoppers a huge catalog to choose from and provides sellers with a bigger base of ready-to-buy customers. Think of multivendor platforms as digital shopping malls. In addition, this application stores the technical infrastructure to support the listing and sale of thousands of products across a vast range of categories through a huge number of sellers with the power to manage their virtual storefronts. The eCommerce business has successfully emerged as a significant business scope in recent years and Entrepreneurs worldwide are trying their best to jump right into this market segment (digital marketing) to make a huge profit. However, most of them struggle

hard to come up with a business idea and i believe my project on designing a multi-vendor ecommerce application will create a market for them. Since majority of business vendors do not produce their own products to sell, reselling can be very difficult when you do not have a market and a multiple other websites are fighting for that same market. For this reason, the dynamics of online shopping will changed to a great extent as many entrepreneurs can discovered my project of multi-vendor marketplace business model as their perfect solution to make their place in the competitive market.

1.2 Problem Statement

My research started after the opening of the Douala grand mall where individual shops comes together in a particular place to selling products to customers, I focused my survey around Douala and Buea where different shop owners or product owners can rapidly connect to a local market. Rather than going for a single sole based shop that might run out of items or do not have particular item(goods and services) at all and the stress of buyers having to walk all through in search of a particular product, the multivendor application has many different shops run by individual owners. As the multi-vendor app owner, you are not responsible for running or managing the shops. Instead, the focus is more towards ensuring seamless storage and delivery of the product.

1.3 Research Questions

- What techniques or method can be used to implement a multi-vendor e-commerce application?
- What are the modules to be implement in this application?
- Why would people want to use my application?

- What will the recommendation system do?

1.4 Objective of the Study

- The main objective of this of this project is to create a market for everyone willing to sell and present their goods and services to customers of interest.
- To ensure the system is reliable to visitors so they buy at the best possible price
- Make sure users are legit and they actually own the item they intend to sell in order to avoid a case of client buying items that was stolen
- To reduce the cost of owning a store where you have to pay monthly bills by making accounts free to its users
- To save time and stress of going to malls, supermarkets and other shopping places and rather seat at home and scroll through your and find the goods and services you want.
- Invoice generation after a successful order
- Sellers contact information and address will be available to buyers so they know who they are dealing with.

1.5 Scope of Study

In this project, I have to study how a mall functions and the process of shop or seller's management and digital marketplace system. Understanding that the most important participant in sales is the customer ["cs-cart"], sellers or web store owners have to aim on creating the best stores for buyers since clients will always search for good online shops that will make shopping convenient and rapid. Also, a multi-vendor ecommerce system enables users to customize, manage and make any changes in his items that will increase virtual store popularity with different keywords.

1.6 Significance of Study

Marketing is a field that will never lose its grounds because people will always trade and this trade comes in different ways which my project offers a free market to its clients such that they can successfully run their store in a virtual environment and gain more customers at a distance and worldwide just by uploading available items to be sold. Owning a store in a mall like Grand mall can be very hectic and expensive for a developing business so this project also comes in to provide possibility to these starting sellers to have a market with any extra fee provided with a wider range of buyers in all locations. In addition, it will equally save stress of buyers going to the market and spending hours just to end up not buying what they went to buy because of lack of information on which store is having that particular good at the point in time.

1.7 Limitation of Study

The main limitation in this research is time and resource, because the time required to build and develop this application is not enough for all components of the app to be implemented, however making it not possible to implement all components and deployment of this application.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

There will be always sellers having products to sell and buyers willing to buy, some will have to travel to find a market while some buyers will have to go through crowds just to get particular products. Other sellers do have products but don't have the market where they can successfully sell their products.

2.1 Definition of key words

a) Visual Studio Code:

Visual Studio Code is a streamlined code editor with support for development operations like debugging, task running, and version control. It aims to provide just the tools a developer needs for a quick code-build-debug cycle and leaves more complex workflows to fuller featured IDEs, such as Visual Studio IDE.

b) PHP myAdmin:

phpMyAdmin is one of the most popular applications for **MySQL database management**. It is a free tool written in PHP. Through this software, you can create, alter, drop, delete, import and export MySQL database tables.

c) XAMPP:

XAMPP is a free and open-source cross-platform web server. XAMPP is simply a local host or server that is used to test clients or websites before publishing them to a remote web server. The XAMPP server software on a local computer provides an appropriate environment for testing MYSQL, PHP, Apache, and Perl projects.

d) Jupyter:

The *Jupyter Notebook App* is a server-client application that allows editing and running via a web browser. The *Jupyter Notebook App* can be executed on a local desktop requiring no internet access (as described in this document) or can be installed on a remote server and accessed through the internet.

2.2 Conceptual Literature

Digital trading places change traditional approaches to product promotion due to the ability to accurately assess market volumes, competitors, choose the most effective promotion strategy and marketing instruments. With the development of digital marketing, online stores are increasingly being used not as an intermediary between the seller and the buyer, but as an online sales platform. This led to the emergence of a new format of trade and the transformation of the traditional e-commerce market, changes in the role of sellers, active participation of the buyer in the formation of supply and marketing. The use of digital instruments for competitive analysis of a potential niche of the product facilitates promotion and allows to evaluate the potential level of income, optimize promotion instruments in the current period. The article is aimed at identifying a set of strategic marketing instruments for promoting the product on the marketplace. The article on the basis of competitive analysis cases discusses practical aspects of using digital instruments to determine sales potential in a particular market. The main strategies for product

promotion and the advantages of each strategy are defined. Based on the practical sales case of three types of products using a digital platform and instruments for promoting these products, the efficiency of each instrument has been identified. The effect of promoting each product is evaluated using conversion rates, rating, sales ratio using digital platform advertising campaigns to organic sales of each product. It is proved that thanks to digital platforms, the manufacturer, the seller of the product in real time in the current period has the opportunity to redistribute the costs of various marketing instruments of promotion and ensure sales growth, product rating. The product sales performance indicators (conversion, rating, and volumes) allow to adjust the promotion strategy (update the brand, content, listing) in the current period, which reduces the risk of shortage in sales. The author emphasizes that further research should be directed towards

2.3 Empirical Literature

Nowadays, the usage of Internet is very common. It acts as the channel to search for information and to shop online. Taylor Nelson Sofres' Report 2001 (as cited in Hannula & Chuck, 2003) stated that the percentage of worldwide online shoppers has increased by 50% from 2000 to 2001. Consumers' perceived benefits comprises of the sum of online shopping advantages or satisfactions that meet their demands (Wu, 2003). There are six perceived benefits considered in this research, which are Webpage design, product choice, price, convenience, customer service, and product quality.

Although Internet shopping mall deals with physical and digital products or services, the basic concept of product quality is not different from that of traditional commerce. The most influential factors appear to be product quality and product variety. Product quality means the actual functionality of the product, consistency between the quality specification of Internet shopping mall and real quality of the physical product. Variety is the assortment or a range of goods available from a shop. Customers are likely to visit an Internet shopping

mall with various and high-quality products. If the product quality meets their expectation, customers tend to regard the Internet shopping mall as useful and continue to visit it. Keeney posited that maximization of product quality is one of the “fundamental objectives” for showing more content.

Online shopping as a new medium for retailing creates a number of different advantages. One of these is that it is considered to be more convenient to shop online compared to the traditional way of shopping. The convenience at tributes that online shopping provides are less effort, being able to shop at home, time saving and being able to shop at any time of the day.

Chapter 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Procedure

The Iterative agile model is chosen as my methodology for this project. There are 5 phases in the in the iterative model and 3 springs in the agile as shown below.

The iterative waterfall approach emphasize a structure and a well-defined progression between each phase with feedbacks at each stage. Each phase consist of a defined set of

activities and deliverables that must be accomplished before going to the next phase or step.

Agile development methodology, software developments sprint develop process management and scrum sprints

AGILE DEVELOPMENT

Agile simply means continuous incremental improvement through small and frequent releases. The term Agile is most commonly associated with software development as a project management methodology. Unlike traditional approaches to product development, which have notoriously long development cycles, agile principles encourage minimizing the time between ideation and launch. The idea is to get a working product in the hands of customers as soon as possible.